

Role of Average Energy and Plane Waves in the Schrodinger Equation

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 8, 2019

In an earlier note (1), it was argued the time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written in a momentum form by using $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ = wavefunction and $V(x) = \sum_p V_p \exp(ipx)$. This leads to an equation for each plane wave of the form:

$\frac{p^2}{2m} f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k = E f_p$ ((1)). In this note, we try to argue that ((1)) does not need to follow from the time-independent Schrodinger equation, but rather seems to be a consequence of f_p , which is related to conditional probability $P(p/x)$.

Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

The time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written as:

$$(-\frac{1}{2m}) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((2))$$

If one writes both $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as a Fourier series and collects coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$, one obtains:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_k = E f_p \quad ((1)).$$

It is argued that because each f_p uses the same "E", there is a resonance and that equation ((1)) is of the form of a $\frac{d}{dt} f_p(t)$ equation leading to $\exp(iEt)$ for each p wave.

If one multiplies ((1)) by f_p and sums, then:

$$\text{Average kinetic energy} + \sum_{p \text{ and } j} f_p f_{(-j+p)} V_j = E$$

so the second term on the left should be the average potential energy $\int dx W(x) W(x) V(x)$.

Result Not Using the Schrodinger Equation

The focus of this note is to see whether ((1)) may be obtained without using the Schrodinger equation. Consider writing $V(x)$ as a Fourier series and assume each V_j (Fourier transform) actually represents a momentum in terms of its effect on an incoming momentum. Then, by conservation of momentum a collision with V_j could change a particle with momentum k to $k+j$. Here we are working in one dimension. In such a case, the particle would be represented by $\exp(ikx)$ as V_j is associated with $\exp(ijx)$. Assume a particle is released into a region where $V(x)$ is present. It will scatter from one momentum state into another, and if a steady state result

ensues, there will be a weight f_p for each momentum state. Thus, the conditional probability $P(p/x)$ may be written as:

$$P(p/x) = f_p \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad \text{where } W(x) = \text{normalization constant} = \sum \text{over } p f_p \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

If a resonance exists, one may consider different f_k 's reacting with V_j 's to form a particular f_p i.e.

$$\sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_k \quad ((4))$$

((3)) is an unusual term as it involves potential energy somehow through V_j and probability through f_k . (The overall probability to have a certain p is f_p^* , but f_p is a conditional probability related to having a particular p at a point x . It is possible to show that one may go from conditional probabilities related to f_p , to non-conditional probability $P(p)=f_p^*f_p$. This has been argued in (2).)

Now, given a particular f_k , it can combine with any V_j to produce different f_l 's. If f_p is related to a conditional probability at x by ((3)), then different f_p 's represent the relative probabilities for f_k to combine with a particular V_l . Thus, one expects:

$$f_k V_j \quad \text{related to } f_{(k+j)} \quad \text{with no other factor depending on momentum} \quad ((5))$$

Thus, there are different probabilities for f_k combining with different Fourier transforms V_l . One must be careful, however, because one is not only dealing with probabilities, but with energy, which is taken to be separate from probability. Thus,

$$p^*p/2m f_p + \sum_{k+j=p} V_j f_k = E f_p \quad ((6))$$

Here E and not E_p is used on the right hand side of ((6)) because of ((5)). If one used E_p , which would be a function of p , it would imply there is something more than conditional probability f_p governing ((5)). The left hand side of ((6)) contains all energy pieces related to p , so the right hand side should reflect that the conditional probability to have a p at x is proportional to f_p with the constant being independent of p . This constant must be average energy due to the nature of the left hand side of ((6)). From ((6)), however, one obtains the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

It should be noted that since one is dealing with a single particle, the f_k 's are being produced at different points in time. The sum in ((6)) cycles through all f_k 's for each p . Thus, ((6)) might be interpreted as carrying time information with $iE f_p = d/dt f_p(t)$. Then, all f_p 's would carry a factor of $\exp(iEt)$ representing cycling in a time of $1/E$. Here E is the average energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue in this brief note that one may obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation by considering scattering off a potential $V(x)$ written as a Fourier series. It is assumed that the particle scattering has the form $\exp(ipx)$ and that the p wave carries a weight of f_p related to a conditional probability $P(p/x)$. A particular $f_k \exp(ikx)$ may scatter with different Fourier transform values V_l with conditional probabilities related to $f(k+l)$. Given that one writes the interaction as $V_l f_k$, energy and not only probability is involved. Thus, one is led to $p^2/2m f_p + \sum_{j+k=p} V_j f_j = E f_p$ where E , the average energy, does not depend on p .

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and Schrodinger Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Wavefunction Squared as Spatial Probability Density (preprint, zenodo, 2018)